

Translation and Image Cultivation of Governmental Publicity in Zhaoqing in the Era of Digital Intelligence

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Abstract: As a bridge for communication between China and the world, governmental publicity plays a pivotal role in driving economic upgrading and enhancing openness in Zhaoqing. Thanks to the latest development of digital intelligence innovations, a new trend in China's international communication utilizes digital media and artificial intelligence technologies to globally disseminate China's technology, culture, and values, thereby strengthening China's influence in the global communication arena. Under the impetus of the "digital intelligence era", the translation strategies and image cultivation for Zhaoqing's governmental publicity are key to bettering the city's international image. Despite the rapid progress and remarkable achievement in international publicity, Zhaoqing needs to establish a translation strategy framework that is tailored to local realities, leveraging diversified communication platforms to convey its unique voice to the world. This approach aims to achieve high-quality development in governmental publicity translation and further construct a favorable international image for Zhaoqing in the digital intelligence era.

Keywords: Digital Intelligence Era, High-Quality Development, International Publicity, Translation Strategies.

I. INTRODUCTION

Located in the west-central region of Guangdong Province of China, Zhaoqing city is one of the first batches of excellent tourist cities and famous historical and cultural cities in China, in addition to being a key member of the prosperous Pearl River Delta, and an emerging star in the Guangdong-Hongkong-Macao Greater Bay Area. The increasing international exposure requires a corresponding publicity strategy to better meet with the challenges thus seize the opportunities.

The advent of the "digital intelligence era" has brought new challenges and demands to governmental publicity translation and dissemination. First, this era has transformed China's technological trajectory from following to leading, necessitating not only the communication of technological achievements but also the promotion of related policies, regulations, and cultural values. In the context of increasingly frequent global cultural exchanges, governmental publicity translation serves as a critical bridge between China and the world. The "digital intelligence era" imposes higher standards of accuracy, requiring complex information to be conveyed with precision in both form and content to enhance the international community's understanding of China's developmental model and policy direction.

Second, the "digital intelligence era" emphasizes a balance between localization, regional adaptation, and globalization. High-quality governmental publicity must transcend linguistic and cultural barriers to disseminate Chinese governmental information and cultural essence to nations with diverse cultural contexts, fostering broader global acceptance and understanding.

Third, the era introduces greater strategic depth and subtlety in content, channels, and outcomes. Accelerated information flow demands that translation work be efficient and timely. Governmental publicity translation must not only be precise

but also consider the cultural backgrounds and reception habits of target audiences, effectively delivering messages in accurate target languages.

Finally, local governmental publicity platforms must adopt a diversified matrix of channels. This is both an inevitable requirement of media convergence trends and a crucial approach for enhancing the effectiveness of governmental information dissemination, shaping a positive government image, and addressing public opinion challenges. This necessitates local governments to utilize diversified communication methods and expand channels to achieve more effective international communication outcomes.

From the perspective of the "digital intelligence era", translation strategies for local governmental publicity hold significant theoretical and practical value in improving the effectiveness of governmental communication efforts. As a major city in Guangdong Province and the Greater Bay Area, Zhaoqing has made remarkable achievements in cultural tourism and international exchanges through its rich historical and cultural resources. However, certain issues still need to be addressed: the quality of Zhaoqing's publicity materials is subpar; qualified translation talent is insufficient; translation products are often rigid, lack specificity, and fail to account for subtle cultural differences. These issues severely hinder the high-quality development of its governmental publicity. This paper aims to identify problems in Zhaoqing's local publicity materials and propose translation and dissemination strategy frameworks to guide translation practices. By adhering to the principle of high-quality development, fostering synergy between domestic and international publicity, innovating dissemination approaches, and leveraging local characteristics while targeting global markets, we aim to expand communication channels, harness the advantages of emerging media, and provide practical suggestions for the aim of better telling China's story and Zhaoqing's story to the world.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

International communication or international publicity refers to the dissemination of information about a country's culture, history, politics, and economy through various channels and methods, aiming to shape a positive national image and influence on the international stage. It is a cross-linguistic, cross-cultural, and cross-regional activity of information dissemination and exchange, intended to introduce China to the global community, enabling a better understanding of the country and fostering a favorable international environment for China's economic construction and social development (Hu, 2023).

Since the founding of the People's Republic of China, the Chinese government has prioritized translation work for international publicity, which has drawn significant attention from academia. Scholars have explored various aspects, such as the nature and characteristics of international publicity translation (Xiong, 2018), strategies and methods (Yu, 2016), translator subjectivity (Li, 2012), and the relationship between foreign publicity translation and ideology (Hu & Jia, 2010). Zhang Hong emphasizes that to gain recognition and appreciation of China's unique culture from international audiences, translations must align with target audience expectations and adopt discourse styles that resonate with them, ultimately achieving the objectives of international publicity (Zhang, 2020).

However, most existing studies remain at a macro level and fail to focus on the specific realities of local governmental publicity efforts. Even when studies address local governmental translation, they tend to rely on case studies or error analyses, offering limited practical guidance for local implementation given the vast differences between cities across the country. Researches focused on Zhaoqing's publicity translation are still in the primary stage with only a number of publications. This highlights the need to develop a translation strategy framework tailored to Zhaoqing's local practices in governmental publicity, providing specific insights for translation practice.

III. COMMON ERRORS IN GOVERNMENTAL PUBLICITY TRANSLATION

With the arrival of the "digital intelligence era", the speed and breadth of information dissemination have reached unprecedented levels, presenting more complex challenges on governmental publicity translation. The quality of translation directly impacts the effectiveness of international communication and even affects the shaping of Zhaoqing's international image. Therefore, when analyzing common errors in governmental publicity translation, it is essential to address the major issues in current translation practices. This analysis will focus on three aspects: political stance, cultural choices, and knowledge-based errors, providing a foundation for the improvement strategies that will follow.

3.1 Political Stance Errors

In the digital intelligence era, the more accessible and efficient dissemination of information places higher demands on translators' skills and qualifications. Translators must thoroughly understand and align with national policies and guidelines to prevent political errors, particularly in highly sensitive contexts involving Hong Kong, Macao, and Taiwan. For example, "中国大陆" should be translated as "Chinese mainland", avoiding the Western media's phrasing of "mainland China". Similarly, "中国共产党" should be rendered as "Communist Party of China (CPC)" rather than "Chinese Communist Party (CCP)", and "计划生育政策" must be translated as "family planning policy" instead of "birth control policy". These tasks require translators to enhance their political awareness, recognize the critical importance of international communication, and treat translation as a matter of paramount significance in foreign affairs.

3.2 Cultural Selection Errors

Significant differences between Chinese and Western cultures necessitate careful attention when translating culturally loaded terms to ensure the use of idiomatic expressions in the target language and avoid potentially embarrassing errors. For example, the term "宣传" should not be literally translated as the mechanical dictionary equivalent of "propaganda", as the latter carries negative connotations in English; instead, "publicity" or "communication" is more appropriate. Similarly, "民主党派" should be translated as "other political parties" rather than "democratic parties" to avoid the unnecessary connotations. Additionally, the phrase "解放前", which may be unfamiliar to foreign readers, should not be directly rendered as "before liberation" but rather contextualized as "before 1949" or "before the establishment of the People's Republic of China" for the convenience of international readers.

3.3 Knowledge-Based Errors

During translation, it is essential to thoroughly research and understand unfamiliar terms or concepts to determine their precise meaning, avoiding errors caused by superficial interpretation. Some translators tend to neglect the subtle difference in languages and are prone to hasty equivalents which might be totally baffling in another language, or cause confusion. For instance, the infrastructure project "二广高速" Guangning and Huaiji sections in Zhaoqing was once mistakenly translated as "Guangdong-Guangxi Expressway", when it actually refers to the "Erenhot-Guangzhou Expressway". In Chinese "二广高速" and "两广高速" might sound quite similar but they are completely different concepts. Similarly, "中山大学" should be translated as "Sun Yat-sen University" following the Wade-Giles Romanization system, while "中山学院" should be rendered as "Zhongshan Institute", not "Sun Yat-sen Institute". Furthermore, translating official titles like "局长" (bureau chief) requires careful consideration of administrative levels to determine the appropriate equivalent given the complicated government ranking systems. For example, the "局长" of the Duanzhou District Economic and Trade Bureau should be translated as "section chief", the "局长" of Zhaoqing Municipal Commerce Bureau as "director", and the "局长" of Guangdong Provincial Sports Bureau as "director-general". The Chinese title 局长 could refer to different levels of government ranks and translators must be alert to their specific contexts to avoid embarrassing misunderstandings. This is after all the Chinese culture of government official ranks which might be unique in its own way. Translators should bear in mind the subtle differences and avoid pitfalls when transforming information from one language to another.

IV. PRINCIPLES FOR GOVERNMENTAL PUBLICITY TRANSLATION IN ZHAOQING IN THE DIGITAL INTELLIGENCE ERA

In governmental publicity translation, understanding the fundamental principles is crucial. Considering the characteristics of communication in the "digital intelligence era", translation practices must not only meet the requirement of accurate information transmission but also be audience-centered, innovating expressions to enhance international communication effectiveness. Based on an analysis of existing research and the practical demands of external publicity translation, this paper will explore the core principles that Zhaoqing's governmental publicity translation should follow in the context of the "digital intelligence era".

4.1 The "Three Closeness" Principle in International Publicity

Huang Youyi proposed that international publicity translation should "align closely with China's development realities, address closely the international audience's need for information about China, and adhere closely to their cognitive habits". This "Three Closeness" principle holds significant value for guiding the practice of publicity translation and is a standard acknowledged by many professionals in the field. The "Three Closeness" principle has become a widely accepted theoretical foundation for international publicity translation research in China (Huang, 2004).

4.2 The "Country-First" Principle in International Publicity Translation

International publicity translation must prioritize the maintenance of the nation's and local governments' positive image, adhering to a "Country-First" approach. Translators must always remember that national and local interests take precedence, avoiding any translation choices that could harm these interests or reduce the effectiveness of the publicity. Any negligence or error could potentially be detrimental to the country's image and thus runs counter to the goal of international communications by the government's efforts.

Starting with the most basic step of translation: choice of words. When selecting vocabulary, it is crucial to avoid pejorative or culturally inappropriate terms. For example, to describe the city's magnificent scenery, the term "beautiful" is often insufficient as it fails to capture the picturesque quality of Zhaoqing's landscape. Instead, "picturesque" "breath-taking" or other formal words might prove more fitting. Similarly, Zhaoqing is often referred to as a "名城" in Chinese, which some translators might translate it literally as "famous city", inadvertently diminishing the city's prestige. A better choice of words would be "prestigious", "eminent" or "renowned" to give the description more strength and significance.

Additionally, skillful use of synonyms can enhance the expressiveness of governmental publicity texts. For instance, the term "发展" (development) frequently appears in such texts and is often repeatedly translated as "development". However, mechanical repetition of this word can make the text monotonous and unengaging as the author once read a short paragraph of government brochure which has six "development" in a five-lined paragraph. Very phonetically awkward and consuming to readers. Depending on the context, alternatives such as "growth", "progress", "bettering", or "improvement" can be used to create a more dynamic colorful and appealing narrative.

International publicity texts should be guided by reader response and communication effectiveness. Careful selection of vocabulary and expressions, rather than a rigid and blind adherence to the original Chinese structure, is essential for achieving the goals of foreign publicity and for crafting translations that resonate with the target audience in a different language and culture.

V. CHALLENGES IN GOVERNMENTAL PUBLICITY TRANSLATION IN ZHAOQING DURING THE DIGITAL INTELLIGENCE ERA

The "digital intelligence era" has not only brought advancements in information dissemination technology but also posed unprecedented challenges to governmental publicity translation. In the process of governmental publicity translation, Zhaoqing must adapt to the trends of digital technologies and smart communication while addressing bottlenecks in lacks of qualified talents, expanding media channels, and improving information transmission quality. Based on the current challenges in international publicity practices, this paper further analyzes the key issues affecting translation outcomes and explores their underlying causes.

5.1 Imbalance Between Supply and Demand for Translation Talent Amid International Market Expansion Needs

In recent years, the demand for high quality translation talent in Zhaoqing has been rising in fields such as governmental publicity, cultural tourism, and international trade. However, the supply of qualified translation talent in Zhaoqing's local talent market remains insufficient. Compared to larger cities, the growth in demand for translators in Zhaoqing is notable, but the overall talent pool is still rather limited and inadequate to the scale of social and economic development. The imbalance stems from two main reasons:

Firstly, while Zhaoqing benefits from its advantageous location at the intersection of mid-western Guangdong and the Pearl River Delta, it faces challenges in attracting and retaining qualified translation professionals. Secondly, although local universities in Zhaoqing offer translation courses, the number and quality of trained translators fall short of meeting market demands, thus amateur translators are called for the jobs which inevitably results in frequent errors and

incompetent instances. Acquiring high quality translation professionals still tops the agenda of international publicity enhancement in the city.

5.2 Insufficiently Expanded Channels for International Publicity Translation and Reliance on Traditional Media Models

Based on the visual grammar framework proposed by Kress and Van Leeuwen (1996), foreign publicity translation should leverage visual translation capabilities and multimodal integration, enhancing the application of technological tools to disseminate Chinese culture through multiple channels (Yuan, 2024). However, in the digital intelligence era, Zhaoqing's international publicity translation efforts still primarily rely on traditional manual translation. While this approach ensures a certain level of accuracy and quality, it fails to fully harness the advantages of modern technology and multimodal communication, especially the latest development of Chat GPT or other AI based large language models (LLMs).

Specifically, Zhaoqing's international publicity translation channels remain relatively narrow, confined mainly to traditional text-based translations and printed publications, only recently expanded to the social media channels. In general, the city still lacks a broad presence on digital media, social media, and other emerging platforms. Moreover, translation content often focuses on official documents and tourism promotional materials, with insufficient exploration and diverse representation of Zhaoqing's rich cultural heritage and unique charm. Large amount of work still remains to be done to raise the effectiveness of international exposure of Zhaoqing on condition of joined efforts of various international publicity cultivation measures.

5.3 Inconsistent Translation Quality Undermines Zhaoqing's Global Outreach Efforts

While Zhaoqing's cultural publicity benefits from its rich regional characteristics and cultural depth, many translators lack a deep understanding of Zhaoqing's culture. As a result, translations of local materials often misinterpret or entirely overlook expressions unique to the region. Some translations appear overly rigid, lack strategic innovation, and rely excessively on traditional methods such as literal translation. For an example, 端砚 as the most cultural and historical iconic representation of the city, has quite a few translations, from "Duan Inkstone", "Duanzhou Inkstone", "Duan Ink Slab", to the Chinese Pinyin "Duanyan". Additional explanation of footnotes are needed to better facilitate the underlying cultural significance depending on different international occasions. The government authorities should organize related seminars to coordinate and finalize the versions of translation to unify the publicity efforts.

This lack of consideration for the cultural context and reading habits of the target language audience often fails to accurately convey the unique cultural essence of Zhaoqing. Consequently, international readers are unable to fully appreciate the city's cultural appeal, and Zhaoqing struggles to capture global attention or generate resonance. This not only hampers the interest of foreign tourists but also risks creating misunderstandings about the city.

VI. STRATEGIES FOR IMAGE CULTIVATION IN ZHAOQING IN THE DIGITAL INTELLIGENCE ERA

Facing the multiple challenges of the "digital intelligence era", Zhaoqing's governmental publicity translation work needs to advance from both theoretical and practical perspectives, exploring effective strategies for image building. Supported by innovative technological means and a multimodal communication framework, governmental publicity translation is not merely a language conversion but a cultural bridge. Based on this understanding, this paper proposes a series of concrete strategic suggestions to offer new inspirations for the cultivation of Zhaoqing's public image in the global settings.

6.1 Integrating Regional Corpora and Establishing Unified Translation Standards

On the one hand, as a distinctive aspect of Zhaoqing's regional identity, Lingnan culture entails a vast amount of cultural documentation, yet the city has not developed a comprehensive cultural translation corpus. Relevant government departments in Zhaoqing should prioritize the construction of a regional cultural corpus, integrating existing materials, which plays a critical role in the translation of governmental publicity materials.

On the other hand, Zhaoqing lacks standardized translation guidelines for certain technical terms. Different translation agencies, translators, or teams often employ varying vocabulary, phrases, or expressions for the same terms, resulting in inconsistent translations across different contexts. In the context of the digital intelligence era, to improve the quality of governmental publicity translation in Zhaoqing, relevant departments can adopt modern automated proofreading tools and

other technological models. These tools can provide technical support for reducing basic errors by identifying issues with spelling, punctuation, and grammar, providing unified terminology and consistent name branding, significantly decreasing the risk of human oversight.

Additionally, authorities should compile a standardized translation manual to unify the translation of key place names, terminology, and proper nouns, avoiding confusion and discrepancies in translation. By combining standardized guidelines with automated proofreading tools, the frequency of basic errors can be substantially reduced, improving the accuracy and consistency of translations. This, in turn, enhances foreign visitors' positive impressions and satisfaction with Zhaoqing.

6.2 Developing Professional International Publicity Teams and Optimizing Pragmatic Adaptability

Governmental publicity involves strong policy dimensions, requiring translators to possess not only a profound sense of national duty but also solid knowledge of local history, culture, and economics. Reducing cultural and language errors is crucial to improving translation quality and enhancing the reading experience of international audiences.

Relevant departments should introduce cross-cultural adaptation review mechanisms into the translation process to ensure that translations not only conform to the linguistic habits of the target language but also meet the understanding needs of audiences from different cultural backgrounds. To achieve this, authorities can establish a multi-tiered review system by inviting experts or consultants with native speaker proficiency in the target language to review translation content, thereby optimizing cultural and pragmatic adaptability.

Management departments should also organize regular cross-cultural communication training for translators, covering aspects such as idiomatic expressions, values, and contextual requirements in the target culture. Through systematic learning and practice, translators can gain a deeper understanding of the target culture, avoiding mechanical errors caused by literal translation and improving the acceptability of Zhaoqing's translated content.

Furthermore, relevant authorities should encourage translators to accumulate extensive practical experience and increase their exposure to the target culture. By conducting field visits and simulating daily communication scenarios in the target language environment, translators can gain deeper insights into the linguistic habits of native speakers and enhance cultural sensitivity in translation.

Authorities could also create regular practice platforms to give translators opportunities to better understand English cultural norms and linguistic conventions. By combining pragmatic training, cultural adaptation reviews, and practical platforms, the occurrence of publicity errors can be significantly reduced, enhancing professional translation standards and cultural adaptability. This approach will help achieve the objectives of international communication, authentically showcasing Zhaoqing's charm and attracting greater international attention.

6.3 Multimodal Integration in International Publicity Translation to Promote Zhaoqing's Cultural Outreach

Zhang (2009) pointed out that media and communication channels combining language, images, and sound often require engaging multiple senses such as vision, hearing, and touch, integrating linguistic and non-linguistic symbols to enable comprehensive, multimodal information dissemination. Within this framework, foreign publicity translation of Zhaoqing's unique culture and social achievements should not be limited to textual conversion but should incorporate images, audio, video, and other media to construct a three-dimensional and vivid cultural communication system.

For instance, when introducing Zhaoqing's Duan inkstone culture, textual descriptions of its craftsmanship and historical value can be complemented with images showcasing the intricate details of the inkstones and videos documenting the entire production process. This approach provides foreign audiences with a holistic, multi-angled understanding of this intangible cultural heritage. By adopting a multimodal strategy, Zhaoqing's historical narratives, folk customs, and natural landscapes can be presented more directly and vividly to international audiences.

Having translated and voice-dubbed materials for Zhaoqing's promotional videos, websites, short videos, and brochures, the author has accumulated substantial experience. However, various challenges remain, particularly in translating Chinese culture and Zhaoqing's distinctive local culture into a foreign language and culture under the context of digital intelligence, where improvements are still much needed.

6.4 Innovating Governmental Translation Strategies to Precisely Convey Zhaoqing's Charm

Innovative translation strategies for governmental publicity should focus on both macro and micro levels to enhance translation quality and effectively communicate Zhaoqing's prestigious city image, thereby increasing its international recognition.

From a macro perspective, three key actions are necessary. First, government leadership is essential, with the Zhaoqing municipal government taking the lead in strengthening macro-level coordination by establishing a governmental translation coordination group responsible for planning, supervising, and managing translation projects. A translation quality rewards fund could be set up to recognize outstanding individuals or teams in governmental translation, while the authorities should also provide translators with authentic and authoritative materials for international publicity translation. Second, educational support is crucial, as Zhaoqing's universities can leverage their resources to offer practical courses in governmental translation, instilling an early awareness of international publicity in students and, by integrating real-world cases from Zhaoqing, teaching effective translation techniques and methods. Third, corporate involvement is vital, with local enterprises playing a key role in driving regional economic development and internationalization by showcasing their innovative achievements, advanced technologies, and high-quality products to highlight Zhaoqing's economic strength and industrial characteristics to the world. Additionally, businesses should actively participate in investment promotion events, utilizing their networks and resources to attract foreign investment and projects to Zhaoqing.

At the micro level, translators should maintain an objective and impartial attitude, avoiding personal biases. They should flexibly apply translation strategies and adhere to the "Three Closeness" principle in international publicity translation practices. This ensures that translations accurately reflect the original text's intent while aligning with the cultural preferences and reading habits of the target audience. Writing in the target language with cultural considerations allows the translations to achieve the intended purpose of international publicity, enhancing Zhaoqing's positive global image and cultural soft power.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study delves into the international publicity of governmental translation and image cultivation of Zhaoqing in the context of the "digital intelligence era", highlighting the critical role of translation strategies and image construction in enhancing the city's international image, promoting economic upgrading, and advancing openness. The findings reveal that although Zhaoqing has made progress in translation and dissemination, it still faces multiple challenges, including an imbalance between supply and demand for translation talent, inconsistent translation quality, and limited translation publicity channels.

In response to these issues, the paper offers strategic recommendations to lay the groundwork for a translation strategy framework tailored to Zhaoqing's local context. The government authorities should coordinate translation activities to unify efforts and consistency of terminology, slogans, culturally loaded terms, and other glossy terms. Fully employ the latest AI technology to ensure adequate quality control of translation works, diversify the media channels to cater to the digital intelligent era trends. In addition, the relevant departments should establish multi-step review processes to guarantee the quality of translation and eliminate potential cultural and linguistic errors. For important publicity materials, it's beneficial to have a native speaker to review the translation to better adjust to the target language readers. Translation professionals also need regular training and seminars to ensure smooth communication and informed with the latest developments of the local government's agenda.

High quality translation is the basis of high-quality international publicity. It helps Zhaoqing city build a favorable global brand image and enhance its economy and commerce at large. Effective communications can assist the local authorities to conduct business trade and tourism promotion campaigns. International businesses tourists are attracted to Zhaoqing after they acknowledge the content and authenticity of publicity materials. Education, cultural communication and mutual understanding between cultures and cavillations will be equally enhanced thanks to the high-quality translation. With collective effort and innovation, Zhaoqing is poised to gradually establish a more distinct international image and achieve high-quality development in governmental publicity during the digital intelligence era.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Huang, Youyi. (2004). Adhering to the Principle of "Three Closeness in International Publicity" and Addressing Difficulties in Foreign Publicity Translation. *International Communication*, (9), 4–6.
- [2] Hu, Fangyi, & Jia, Wenbo. (2010). International Publicity Translation: Rewriting under Ideological Manipulation. *Shanghai Journal of Translators*, (1), 6.
- [3] Hu, Kaibao. (2023). National Foreign Publicity Translation Competence: Components, Current Status, and Future Prospects. *Shanghai Journal of Translators*, (4), 1–7.
- [4] Kress, G. R., & Van Leeuwen, T. (1996). *Reading Images: The Grammar of Visual Design*. New York: Routledge.
- [5] Levy Mmpaignmance improvement program targeting severe sepsis. *Crit Care Med* 38:367–374.
- [5] Li, Chunguang. (2012). On the Harmonious Unity of Audience Centrality and Translator Subjectivity in Foreign Publicity Translation. *Journal of Tianjin Foreign Studies University*, (4), 4.
- [6] Xiong, Daohong. (2018). Border Inspection International Publicity from the Perspective of National Capacity: Characteristics, Problems, and Countermeasures. *International Communication*, (11), 3.
- [7] Yu, Qiuping. (2016). A Discussion on International Publicity Translation Strategies from the Perspective of National Image. *Journal of Xi'an International Studies University*, (1), 4.
- [8] Yuan, Mengqi. (2024). Enhancing the Influence of Chinese Civilization through International Publicity Translation in the Digital Age. *Jiaying Literature*, (13).
- [9] Zhang, Delu. (2018). Exploring an Integrated Theoretical Framework for Multimodal Discourse Analysis. *The Second Forum on Multimodal and Special Population Discourse Multidisciplinary Research*, Tongji University.
- [10] Zhang, Hong. (2020). "Translation" and "Publicity": Rhetorical Strategies in International Publicity Translation on Local Government Websites. *Language and Culture Forum*, (2), 65–75.